

INTEGRATIVE CLUSTER FOR PREPARING FUTURE DEFECTOLOGISTS FOR INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

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Annotation: This article discusses the integrative cluster of training future speech pathologists for inclusive education

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Today, in the preparation of future defectologists working with children with disabilities in specialized schools and special preschool multidisciplinary organizations, the work is based on the content, tasks, principles of correctional education of defectologists. On this basis, positive changes are currently taking place in children with disabilities as a result of joint education of healthy and unhealthy children.

From foreign experience and practice, changes in such children are known through educational work with healthy children, children with visual impairments, children with visual and hearing impairments, children with mild mental retardation.

It is known that Uzbekistan has approved documents aimed at developing inclusive education for children with special needs, including the procedure for opening primary basic correctional classes for children with special needs in general education schools.

On October 12, the Cabinet of Ministers approved a number of legal acts on the development of inclusive education for children with special educational needs.

The document was developed in accordance with the Decree of the President of October 13, 2020 "On measures to further improve the education system for children with special educational needs."

The concept for the development of inclusive education in the state education system for 2020-2025 includes the following main priorities for the development of inclusive education in Uzbekistan, improving the education system for children with special educational needs and improving the quality of educational services provided to them:

- Development and approval of requirements for the premises of educational institutions for children with special needs;

- to carry out measures to provide these educational institutions with the necessary literature, teaching aids, material and technical base and equipment for teaching various professions;
- organizing an inclusive education system, providing educational institutions with special equipment (lifting devices, ramps, fences, etc.), as well as relevant personnel (special teachers, specialists in psychological and pedagogical support for children);
- phased equipping of boarding schools with special equipment for the adaptation and integration of children with special educational needs, etc.

The resolution approved the regulation on inclusive education of children with special needs in general education institutions. That means:

- goals and objectives of inclusive education;
- the procedure for organizing inclusive education and initial remedial classes in schools and the educational process for children with special needs;
- the procedure for admitting children to inclusive education and primary basic remedial classes;
- Measures to control and manage the quality of education in inclusive education and primary basic remedial classes.

Also:

- specialized educational institutions for children with physical, mental, emotional or intellectual disabilities;
- State specialized educational institutions of the sanatorium type;
- The Regulations on the order of individual education at home for children with physical, mental, sensory or mental disabilities, as well as children in need of long-term treatment, have also been approved.

The resolution also provides for measures to organize vocational training courses for children with special needs in specialized educational institutions.

Particular attention is paid to the educational cluster in order to see the effectiveness of the ongoing work on the development of special education. In inclusive education, the main task is to train future defectologists in the educational cluster, to acquire the necessary knowledge, skills and abilities.

Therefore, the introduction of innovations in industry today requires new approaches to existing methods of work. The laws of social development, on the contrary, have common aspects and natural patterns, and in many cases it is better to get ready-made templates in developed countries and use them creatively than to look for specific new ways. Therefore, today in the sectors of the economy, serious attention is paid to the application of innovative practices

that have been tested in world practice and play an important role in the development of industrial sectors of the economy.

One of these innovations is the "cluster model", which is now widely used in Uzbekistan in agriculture, textile and light industry. In the short term, the cluster model is recognized as a promising innovative direction in the economy, and experiments are being carried out to apply this model in other areas. Today, in the conditions of Uzbekistan, the creation of a new mechanism in the higher education system, which should ensure mutual control, competition and mutual benefit between types of education, has become an urgent need.

Given the high social significance of preschool and school education in the sustainable development of society, modern requirements, problems in the system and the fragmentation of education, science and production in their solution today necessitate the transition of continuous pedagogical education to a cluster model of development.

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